

Adapting Positive Psychology Practices in Education to “Positive Education Term”

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Abstract

It is necessary to investigate the development of positive psychology as well as the field of positive education, which has an application of positive psychology in educational settings and schools. Because there is not enough literature support on this subject, especially in Turkey. Practices in educational settings developed quite early at the beginning of the movement known today as positive psychology. The term "positive education" has been used to refer to these methods. The term "positive education" has been interpreted in many ways (Seligman et al. 2009; White and Waters 2015; White 2014). O'Shaughnessy and Larson (2014) argue that positive education is a change in basic assumptions in the approach taken to education and often places the primary emphasis on academic achievement only. It is a combination of learning supported by research in positive psychology and the most effective teaching and learning approaches (White 2014). According to White and Waters (2015) and White (2014), "it is an umbrella term used to describe empirically validated interventions and programs from positive psychology that have an impact on student well-being." ("Why won't it Stick? Positive Psychology and Positive Education") ("Why won't it Stick? Positive Psychology and Positive Education") These authors describe it as "an umbrella term used to describe empirically validated interventions and programs from positive psychology." It adopts an approach that can be considered as training for both the development of traditional skills and the character of the person (Seligman et al. 2009; Seligman 2013). According to White and Murray (2015), "Positive education initiatives in schools exist in three forms:" Programs designed to improve well-being, backed by empirical evidence and scientific research, and that have a real impact on well-being, are topics that require research. Initiative-taking techniques supported by scientific research that can be used in all school mental health programs in schools should be given more importance. Character building education, which includes teachings that focus on specific virtues or values and are based on philosophy or values-based teaching, can thus be conducted.

Keywords: *Positive Psychology, Education, Educational Methods, Educational Psychology*

1. Introduction

argument in Well-Being and Achievement (2013, page 7) that "educational and psychological research has found similar links between higher student self-control and better life outcomes" is an excellent summary of the evidence supporting the impact of positive education. He noted that "educational and psychological research has found similar links between higher student self-control and better life outcomes ." The following is a selection of recent research that proves the value of self-control and perseverance:

IQ was no greater predictor of high school academic performance, absenteeism, or homework practices than self-regulation (Duckworth and Seligman 2005). A longitudinal study of more than 500 secondary school children found that self-control was a significant predictor of homework, classroom behavior, and completion of report cards (Duckworth et al. 2012). Changes in a student's capacity for self-control have been shown to predict changes in their academic performance over a six-month period (Duckworth et al. 2010, 2011). The ability to self-control is also an indicator of childhood health. In a study that followed adolescents as they transition from childhood to adolescence, self-control was found to be an important protective factor against being overweight (Tsukayama and Duckworth 2010). On the other hand, there is a growing need for constructive education programs in schools that can endanger the entire region when viewed more critically (White and Waters 2015). Grassroots welfare is needed in schools, among educators and trainers. Every day, educators are confronted with children who fail in their lessons, who either hold back or are at best doing well.

2. School-Based Positive Psychology

There appears to be a gap between school-based positive psychology, positive education, and well-being initiatives around the world, despite the expansion of these fields of study in schools (Rusk and Waters 2013). It lives in the gap between individual schools' enthusiasm for keeping positive education and the sweeping transformation pursued at the policy level. Even after 15 years of data

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collected, it seems unlikely that positive psychology, positive education and well-being will become policy. Why is this happening? If advocates of positive education are to make considerable progress in government policy, academics need to regularly address the following eight challenges:

- Perspective that substantial amounts of money should be spent educating staff members on various aspects of employee health.
- This is a minor side issue, and many educators perceive it as a departure from important work in reading and developing numeracy.
- At some policy levels there is a feeling that what needs to be addressed is either the welfare of the population or some other issue.
- Scientism is an example of scientific positivism, ignoring the philosophical questions that empiricism is accepted as the only way forward and that explains why well-being should be incorporated into the educational experience.
- Discussions about welfare are not the focus of exceptional governance, which focuses on creating efficient models for making financial and economic decisions. This means that such discussions are not essential for perfect governance.
- Social Economic Situation and Culture It is a reason not to expect a positive change in educational practices.

However, there are not only difficulties at the policy level, but also concerns at the philosophical level. Herein lies the conflict about the well-being of students in educational institutions. Often, many of the people responsible for making wellness programs in schools a reality does so without realizing that health arises from within a school, just as it occurs in a classroom, a drama production, and a sports team. This is true even if healthy living takes place from within a school. Each of these communities has its own standards for behavior, beliefs, and values. A disproportionate number of health and wellness initiatives are straining communities without adequate attention to the pre-existing values of communities before programs are incorporated.

According to Kristjánsson (2013a, b), the burgeoning field of welfare science faces several problems that are fundamental to this field. From her perspective, scholars working in the field need to grapple with these issues to develop coherent frameworks and a vocabulary that will allow

them to bridge the gap that exists between character conversations and preventative strategies for psychological health.

concentration on conformity, which can be seen as qualities of behavior and procedures resembling a factory . In many cases, the organization of schools is based on organized or suppressed conflicts. What kind of graduates can be expected from a typical education system? Many of them seem to have introduced a multitude of changes that , in some cases, supply a narrow view of what is going on in the world . This seems to be the case, despite advances made elsewhere in the world, for example in Finland.

Unless these barriers are removed, I will continue to have doubts about the viability of positive education as a part of public policy. Even considering the World Health Organization's prediction that there will be a global crisis in well-being and that depression will be the leading burden of disease by 2030, or that one person commits suicide every 40 seconds, policies are reluctant to integrate well-being as a driver for and between community development. (WHO 2011).

3. Improvements in Educational Programming in Schools

In a groundbreaking study by Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000a, b) to promote the field of positive psychology, the authors said that schools are a key part of the positive education movement. They were named as “positive institutions” by Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000a, b) and defined them as “organizational systems that focus on learning traditional skills and also aim to move individuals towards better citizenship, responsibility, care, altruism, kindness, civility”: “moderation, tolerance and work ethic” It is common knowledge that a school's culture is an important factor in fostering positive attitudes towards academic achievement.

only a few prominent studies that have tried to conduct systematic case studies of schools as positive institutions, exploring institutional vision , change management, assessment and interventions. These studies have been limited. These include:

Waters, White and Murray (2012), Waters and White (2015) on using appreciative inquiry to promote positive change.

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White and Waters (2015) examples of using the strengths-based approach with students; Kern, Waters, Adler, and White (2015) on measuring well-being in students. ("Why won't it Stick? Positive Psychology and Positive Education.")

Kern, Waters, Adler, and White (2014) on assessing employee well-being in schools. ("(PDF) Building a Positive Institution - ResearchGate")

"Alford and White (2015) on positive school psychology; White, Vrodos and McNeil (2015)" ("(PDF) Building a Positive Institution - ResearchGate")

Schools are increasingly recognizing that they have a role to play in the management of their students' well-being, as well as teaching basic skills such as reading and numeracy. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) estimates that the total number of hours students will spend in school between the ages of 7 and 14 will be approximately 6862, of which 6710 will be needed (OECD 2015, p. 60). In the Australian context, the governments of Queensland, New South Wales and South Australia have recognized that a person's level of happiness and learning ability are intrinsically related. To cite just one example, the Learning and Wellbeing Framework (2012), published by the Queensland Department of Education and Training, claims:

" The best learning environment is one where well-being can be maximized. It is a good school attitude and contributes to making the school an interesting, engaging and friendly environment (2012, p. 3).

Educational programs and frameworks such as Mind Matters, and Kids Matter are examples of social and emotional learning programs that are gaining popularity in schools across the country. These programs encourage students to develop skills such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and social management. Adopting educational policies that focus on student well-being and school culture is a crucial step towards developing inclusive, supportive and safe learning-friendly environments for all students.

Although many school administrators, principals, governing bodies and teachers agree on the importance of students' well-being, it does not appear on the agenda of bureaucratic or system decision makers. level (Furlong et al. 2014; Pesa. edu .au 2016; White 2013, 2014; Weare and Nind 2014).

4. Character Education Applications

Most character education practices are not informed by a scientific knowledge base, which is one of the limitations of the widespread adoption of welfare in politics. This is one of the limitations of the widespread adoption of welfare in politics. This shows a lack of theoretical models or frameworks that can be used to guide the development of character education . Similarly, the teaching profession still seems to seek a standard of practice. This is particularly clear when we compare schooling with other professions such as law, medicine, accounting and nursing, all of which require extensive training and experience.

On the one hand, there seems to be a mismatch between grassroots demand for well-being education in schools and evidence-based programs and the framework, on the other hand, there seems to be a discrepancy between the policy perspectives of different ministries. This challenge is highlighted by the disparity that exists between their research, the link between public policy and the support of grassroots community organizations. This situation has begun to affect both economic and psychological evaluations used in making public policy decisions (Deeming 2013). There is a significant gap between the human part of work, health and well-being, as well as effective evaluations of educational opportunities. In general, population data has been used in the context of health-related public policy for many years. However, the link between the use of population data and increasing educational achievements as a subject area is still largely overlooked (Collins and Foley 2008).

Researchers and practitioners in the positive psychology and positive education movements need to start collaborating with the theoretical barriers and reasons why well-being does not depend on politics to enable sustainable change and support the next 15 years of research. My argument boils

down to this: Unless scientists and practitioners find ways to resolve the main obstacles it faces, the positive education movement will not be able to keep its momentum or have the same kind of impact on education.

By first gaining an awareness of how children think at each stage of their development, educational psychologists can better grasp what children are capable of at each stage of their growth. Educators can use this information to develop instructional strategies and resources tailored to the needs of specific age groups.

5. View from a Cognitive Perspective

The cognitive method has gained immense popularity in recent years, mostly because it considers what aspects of the learning process contribute, such as memories, beliefs, emotions, and motives. This theory supplies support for the concept that an individual can learn because of their own intrinsic motivation and not because of incentives provided by other resources. Cognitive psychology is a field of psychology that looks to understand how individuals think, as well as how they learn, remember, and process information. Educational psychologists with a cognitive perspective are concerned with a wide variety of themes, including but not limited to how children buy the desire to learn, how they remember the information they receive, and how they approach and solve problems. Those who are members of the constructivist school of thought are of the opinion that the person's prior knowledge has the most influence on the way an individual buys new knowledge. This shows that fresh knowledge can only be contributed and grasped in terms of previously accumulated knowledge. The work of psychologist Lev Vygotsky, who introduced concepts such as the zone of proximal development and the instructional scaffold, has had a significant impact on this approach.

6. Experiential Perspective

This perspective places a strong emphasis on the role of a person's own life experiences in deciding how well they grasp added information. This approach is remarkably like the constructivist and

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cognitive views in that it considers the student's experiences, ideas, and emotions as part of the teaching process. This strategy can be used to discover personal significance in what they learn, rather than walking away from experience with the impression that the knowledge is not theirs. Educational psychologists dig deep to understand the learning process more comprehensively. Their focus ranges from the resources used by educators to the specific needs of specific students. In the field of educational psychology, some of these research themes include:

Educational psychologists collaborate with educators, administrators, educators, and students to research the most effective methods to aid individuals in their educational pursuits. Finding strategies for finding children who may need more help, developing programs for children with difficulties, and even inventing new learning methods are often necessary steps in this process.

A significant number of educational psychologists are employed directly by schools. Some hold educator positions such as teacher or professor, while others collaborate with educators to evaluate innovative teaching strategies with their students and design new lesson plans. An educational psychologist can go on to become a counselor and personally aid students in overcoming challenges in their educational pursuits. Research is the focus of the work of various educational psychologists. In addition, educational psychologists often work in the administration of schools or universities. In any of these abilities, they can influence educational practice and helping students buy knowledge in a way that is tailored to their individual needs.

There are three diverse ways that psychological research contributes to our understanding of different teaching strategies. To begin with, strategies can be predicted directly from the natural principles that govern people. For example, we can deduct from psychological research that the reason students find it difficult to learn to divide into fractions is largely due to the habit they have developed as a result of thousands of divisions. Or we can give an example of the habit saw in the past, namely "divide - decrease" or "divide number - result smaller than number". In other words, the habit of "dividing - reducing" or "dividing numbers - getting smaller results is possible for us to consider or choose a strategy that will minimize the impact of interference caused by established routines while maintaining established routines.

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Second, approaches, whether based on psychology or not, can be chosen from real work experience as a starting point. According to this reasoning, it is claimed that a class of fifteen students in primary school produces better results than a class of three or a class of thirty. Therefore, many people think that living in a family environment has more positive effects on a person's character and desire to succeed than life in an institution. For this reason, it is often believed that when trying to become fluent in a foreign language, it is preferable to read easy conversations on easy themes over translations of difficult literary classics that deal with nuanced and complex subjects. Even in such cases, psychology can help by explaining why one strategy is more successful than another, thereby opening the door to new insights into other concerns that have yet to be resolved by experience.

Third, whatever the circumstances, the techniques of assessing knowledge and ability used in psychology can always supply ways to evaluate and confirm or refute the claims made by any approach. For example, educators could not decide, based on their classroom experience, whether it would be preferable to teach the spelling of a pair of synonyms simultaneously or separately over time. This has caused confusion. However, to answer this question for any pair, it is sufficient for enough teachers to use both methods with enough different classes, ensure that everything else is kept constant, and then enough teachers use them. Psychology, which teaches us how to evaluate changes in human nature, also teaches us how to precisely decide the results of any teaching technique. In other words, psychology teaches us how to decide what the consequences of any teaching method are.

The consequences and methods of action of the many forces at work in childhood and throughout a man's life to change his original nature are subjects of study equally proper to the work of a psychologist, a sociologist, or a student of education; but the last two will naturally receive help from everything the first has conducted. We can hope that one day the influence of climate, food, city life, industrial specialization, various forms of family and government, various "works" of schools, and other similar factors will be scrutinized. While studies of such problems are currently crude, speculative, and often misguided, we can hope that they will become more refined in the future.

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The equipment of instincts and abilities that nature supplies apart from education is the foundation on which education is built. Education develops on this foundation. Knowledge of man's unlearned dispositions as a species is essential to knowledge of any individual's unique hereditary traits necessary for effective treatment of that individual. Similarly, knowledge of these trends is necessary for effective planning of education in general. In the last two decades, a great deal of research has been done by psychologists on both the general laws of instinct and their specific nature, the dates of their emergence and extinction, and the conditions under which they can be changed. This research was conducted partly as a deliberate response to this demand and partly because of increased interest in comparative and genetic psychology. Attitude instincts, such as interest and reluctance, should certainly be included here, as well as tendencies towards more overt successful responses.

7. Unlearned Responsiveness Tendencies

The unlearned responsiveness of ants and chickens has unfortunately been studied more carefully than males. In addition, when it comes to human instincts, extreme complexity and a close mix with habits prevent the study of them from yielding completely clear and elegant results, even when done with great care. But an educational theorist or practitioner who should conclude that his haphazard observations of children in homes and schools require no reinforcement from psychologists' research would be making the same sort of not-so-great error as a pathologist or doctor. In other words, the educational theorist or practitioner will be making a mistake. Moreover, the psychologists who criticize them are equally narrow-minded, if for a more altruistic reason, on the grounds that, in their entirety, they do not have the same accuracy and precision as their research on the senses and perceptual judgments.

Research in dynamic psychology is replacing the vague rhetoric and stereotypes of what used to be called "applied psychology" with precise insights into reality far more advanced than common sense alone can provide. The subjects of these studies include the transformation of instincts and abilities into habits and strengths and their development. Reinforcement of a link between situation and response as a result of satisfaction is and is not better than blocking alternative links due to

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discomfort; what the law of diminishing returns from equal application is, what it means, and how it is itself limited; How symptomatic the feelings of success, failure and fatigue are, how symptomatic the feelings of success, failure and fatigue are, is important in this regard.

To better understand this phenomenon, this research is based on the Cultural-Historical Psychology perspective. This perspective argues that things are composites of several different determinants, and that three different dimensions must be considered to define them: their 'history, unity, and contradiction'. (Meira, 2014; Vygotsky, 2007).

The historical context in which public policy evolves into its current forms is a vital part for understanding the nature of the connection that exists between this thing and other things. The liberalization of the market, which began in the sixteenth century, was a crucial factor in the intensification of the argument in favor of minimal intervention in both the economy and society (Santos, 2017). Therefore, because of this, there has been an increase in the growth and accumulation of capital, as well as an increase in the excessive production of goods. This culminated in 1929 with the outbreak of the largest crisis in the history of capitalism, as well as the Second World War, the Cold War, and various other conflicts between countries in the years that followed. As a direct result of this, the hegemonic power structure was reorganized and thousands of people lost their lives (Barroco, Matos, & Orso, 2018).

The objective connections created by such environments shed light on an extremely unfair and privileged way of life production. While conflicts between countries, violence, disintegration of nation-states, destruction of the environment, attacks on social rights escalate, there is also the usurpation of resources and wealth from neighboring countries, and accumulation of capital in the hands of capital. For example, when there is an increase in the number of countries at war with each other, it is there (Barroco et al. 2018).

Economic and Political Environment

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The economic and political environment began to require a stronger involvement of the state in the regulation of social interactions, considering many interests as well as the assurance of social welfare. In this sense, these policies did not come about by chance; rather, they were the result of demands for social protection at a particular point in history. In addition, these policies express a form of social organization and relations of production and as a result reproduce objective realities (Leonardo, Rossato, & Constantino, 2018). In this sense, education policies are the result of the need to guarantee citizens the right to education and the ability to fight for a higher quality of life and conditions of genuine human development. Educational policies in this way stem from the need to secure citizens' right to education. According to Zibetti, Pacfico, and Tamboril (2018), education policies are what reveal educational practices and have a direct impact on the growth of individuals as well as the activities within the education system. According to Lessa and Tonet (2013), with the universalization of education in the 1930s, a rhetoric about social justice, economic distribution, and the potential for social uplift through education spread. This has happened under the banner of Social Welfare. According to Santos (2017), this leads to the development of a dual standardized education model: “one for the wealthier members of society and the other for society as a whole, the working population”. This creates a situation where "school performance determines whether the child will be trained for vocational activities, vocational courses or universities" (Lessa & Tonet, 2013, p.33). Thus, considering these inconsistencies, inequalities between schools are both the product and the producer of the maintenance of class inequalities. Also, this is the case even though some schools are more successful than others.

In Brazil, during the twentieth century, several pre-state proposals for formal education appeared; However, by the end of this century, school education had become a guaranteed right to all citizens, with the end of the dictatorial regime, political and economic reopening, and the struggle for social rights. et al. 2018). After the ratification of the Constitution in 1988, the state took responsibility for the complex societal needs and public policies in the field of education, which at that time had a solid constitutional foundation. Processes and funding to be adopted, as well as laws and

regulations, have been developed through a series of regulatory milestones, and citations are now assigned to various agencies and federative bodies (Barroco et al., 2018).

In this environment, with the regulation of the main axes of public policy, psychology began to gain ground and become necessary in the fields of education, health and social welfare. This trend began at about the same time as the organization of the main axes of public policy. There have been changes in the social prestige of this field of study, as well as a shift in the direction that psychology is heading towards these regulations . In the first decades of the 20th century, psychology was aligned with the ruling class; however, by the end of the century it had come into the service of the popular classes, what has been termed the "proletarianization" of professional activity (Barroco et al., 2018).

8. Researching Educational Policies

On the other hand, in recent years, it has been seen that scientists have concentrated their efforts on the research of education policies. A significant part of the discussion focuses on various government proposals and programs in the field of education. While these proposals and programs are geared towards the regional demands of each country, they are based on assumptions made by international organizations and programs such as the World Bank, the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD), and the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD). United Nations (UN/Unesco), Program for International Student Assessment (Pisa) and others are examples (Zibetti et al., 2018).

The methodological elements of the selected articles reveal that most of the work on the topic consists of documents or literature reviews, with relatively little empirical research or fieldwork. As a result, the importance of documentary analysis is recognized ; however, it is possible that this alone will not be sufficient to understand how education policies are put into practice in the context of political, social and educational realities. According to Mainardes and Tello (2016), given the need to develop knowledge about education policies and to support further studies, investment in

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empirical research is needed. This is because it is necessary to develop knowledge about education policies.

When using the welfare state system, governments are held responsible for satisfying market interests while meeting social security criteria (Lessa & Tonet, 2013). For this reason, it is the duty of the state to ensure social rights, most importantly the right to education, and in connection with this, to adopt education programs appropriate to the realities of the situation (Patto, 1997; Draibe, 2007; Sloan, 2009; Dimenstein, 2011; Gewirtz & Ball, 2011; Leonardo et al., 2016).). As a result, there has been an increase in the number of studies on this phenomenon before the implementation of various education policies.

It is also important to note that most of the countries targeted by the research found are currently developing countries. Such countries are looking to invest in public education and literacy for the quality of their workforce through education plans and programs to enable modernization, improve their weak educational and social indicators, and respond to consumer market demands. This issue is discussed in the work of Castro et al. (2014), Amaral and Monteiro (2013), Farenzena (2012), and Bentancur and Nicolás (2012). According to Saviani (2008), it should be emphasized that the capitalist basis supports the ruling classes and sees educational policy outcomes as subordinate to economic policy outcomes. This is something to consider.

A knowledge assessment is currently being conducted, primarily focusing on using National Assessment Systems to highlight schools with the best results. However, this assessment does not consider the objective and symbolic conditions of educational processes for learning and human development of all relevant actors, whether students, teachers, administrators or other professionals (Leonardo et al., 2018, Zibetti et al., 2018). The discourse of democratizing opportunities and explaining success and failure through the ideology of natural abilities or individual effort is the basis of the principle of meritocracy. (“Educational policies and psychology: a literature review - bvsalud.org”) This discourse has been one of the many contradictions underlying education policies (Dardot & Laval, 2016). Other inconsistencies relate to the link that can be made between the amount of education reached by a population of working age and their ability to take part in the job market and remain active. This issue is discussed in

Munhoz and Melo-(2012) Silva's research paper examining the link between the needs of society, the market and educational institutions. Therefore, the promotion of education, productivity, quality and competitiveness - characteristics of a market economy in an ongoing globalization process - can be experienced at the expense of education for human formation, or in other words, the process of humanization. This is done to promote education at the expense of education designed to make the humanization process practical (Saviani, 2007).

9. Conclusion and Recommendations

It is important to keep in mind that education policies did not develop in a vacuum, but rather linked to other types of policies. Studies emphasize intersectionality with other fields of knowledge, such as architecture and social welfare. The purpose of this research was to make a literature review on education policies, which has been the focus of research during the earlier decade . This was done to decide the degree of connection between School and Educational Psychology. Recent studies have focused on the subject, and among these studies one can see a pattern of researchers' desire to link education with other subfields of knowledge. On the other hand, these studies on school and educational psychology are scarcely enough. The first study subject of the period of individual psychology was child development. Studying the progress of infants, toddlers and children supplied many opportunities for instructive moments. Students were encouraged to examine the complexity of heredity and environment, and their thinking was shifted from black-and-white, inflexible ways of thinking to grayer, more flexible perspectives because of the predominant nature versus nurture. They were also given the ability to perceive the control they might have over their own growth as a result. The study of psychology can help our students mature into collaborative and sympathetic members of society. Students have an ardent desire to understand not only themselves but also those around them; As teachers, we can help them develop a sense of self-awareness and insight, develop social and emotional skills such as the ability to work together and communicate effectively, and expert academic skills such as the ability to conduct scientific research. There is a need for more literature studies on this subject, especially in Turkish.

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